

ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING SERVICES IN ZANZIBAR: A CASE OF ABDULRAHMAN AL-SUMAIT UNIVERSITY AND ZANZIBAR UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: University learners do face many challenges and fail to cope with university life challenges and become the sufferers of psychosocial problems including emotional instability and finally lead to incompetent workers. The ability to resolve their personal and social problems depend much provision of quality guidance and counselling service. This study there for, assessing the quality of guidance and counselling services at Higher Learning Institutions in Zanzibar, focusing on the case of ABDULRAHMAN AL-SUMAIT University and Zanzibar University (ZU). The specific objective of the study was: to identify the nature of guidance and counselling services commonly provided at Zanzibar University and ABDULRAHMAN AL-SUMAIT University, The study employed descriptive design using qualitative research approach during the process of gathering and analysing the data. Purposive sampling technique and random sampling were used and total of 50 respondents were involved in the study. The sample included lectures, counsellor, administrators and learners in two Universities in Zanzibar. Data was collected through interviews where the finding revealed that, counselling facilities which provide counselling service are inadequate and improper in managing the counselling session, however there are counsellors in both Universities with minimum counselling training of resolving learners' psychosocial problems. It was also revealed that both Universities are providing guidance and counselling services mainly categorized into individual, group, social, personal, career and academic, though, there low attendance of learners in seeking for guidance and counselling service was also noticed ,The findings of the study, it was recommended that, Tanzanian Universities should have a uniformity in provision of quality guidance and counselling services through establishment of policies, guide lines, and being supervised by professional boards. Also, placement of highly qualified psychological counsellor at universities as a strategy of strengthening the quality of effective guidance and counselling services.

Keywords: counselling. Guidance, quality, university, university counsellor, learner.

1. INTRODUCTION

University life is a complex social and academic interaction among youths, whereby most of the learners are adolescents and young adults who are socially and economically unsettled (Juma: 2018). In this regard, the adolescents may also try all sorts of adjustment mechanisms to get their needs fulfilled. Additionally, learners in the Universities are not homogeneous

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group but have stratified social, economic, political and ethnic background (Ajow: 2010). Thus, Guidance and counselling services at the University acts as the interactive process that co-joins a susceptible learner at needs of help and enable him/her to grow more efficiently as well as deal the reality of his/her environment .

University guidance and counselling service have benefits to the learners in learning process such as assisting learners in developing effective interpersonal relationship, enhance personal development, assist in acquiring self- knowledge and of others, develop decision making and problem solving skills ,prepare students for the challenge that may face through academic in career and personal/social ,encourage facilitative ,co-operative peer interaction and assure equitable access to educational opportunities (Biswalo:1996) . University counsellor have a duty to assist learners on job application and interview, to engage in psychological tests and other testing, advise on study techniques and may provide group counselling and individual counselling. Also, the quality and characteristics of counsellor are significant in creating a therapeutic alliance with clients(chiresi 2006) . According to Mkinde (1986) identified the quality of effective therapists as having self-respect and appreciation with the ability of self-help and helping others and allowing others to feel powerful with them. Effective therapists are open to change, exhibit a willingness and courage to leave the security of the known if they are not satisfied with the way they are. Besides, therapists also make decisions about how they would like to change, and work toward becoming the person they want to become, that is, an effective counsellor has life-oriented choices.

(Ackumey. 1989), argued that, effective guidance and counselling service counselling in university must have a conducive environment for the good growth, mental health, and psychological wellbeing of the learners to acquire a good and high-quality education in university. This means that University counselling environment should allow learners to be guided and counselled in a positive way that will support their self-determination, self- esteem and self-efficacy and inculcate self-independence and freedom when they face any challenge. In line with this guidance and counselling service must have program that may build positive relationship between counsellor and learner by emphasize openness on the part of learners and to be redness to discuss their problem being presented

Furthermore University based guidance and counselling service counsellor must be multicultural by consider the age, background, health status, religion of the client and bearing in mind diversity of the learners is characteristic in learning institution (Mkinde 1987) and bearing in mind that individuals differ in all aspect of life, thus each learner has unique problems and counsellor needs to help them with their uniqueness with different therapeutic process. (Njeri,2007) emphasized on multicultural and practice in helping learners, where effective guidance and counselling service must led by professional counsellor who is responsible for coordinating guidance and counselling program to emphasize on this, not every tutor in university setting can be assigned to counsel learners, that is, counsellor is expected to have at least Bachelor degree or Masters in Guidance and Counselling to possess all necessary theoretical and practical counselling background, skill and techniques which are required in helping learners to develop their potential.

The global concern related to guidance and counselling service in educational institutions have led to interests in studying discipline management in most universities. Studies from the past decades affirm that availability of G&S service globally including Hong Kong, Britain, United States has benefits on managing discipline issues in Universities (Garner, 2000)

In Africa, This idea of guidance and counselling service was legalized in 2002 where the curriculum of MOEVIT directed the School, Colleges and Universities to establish counselling unit to address student needs and challenges. This was expected to help the learners at higher learning institutions to identify their problems and find better ways through professional counselling available in their academic institutions (MoEVT 2002). In Tanzania and Zanzibar in particular, has legalized provision of guidance and counselling service to its education institution through the education and vocational training however, guidance and counselling service were introduced in schools in late the 1990s, followed by high institutions at 2020s. the guidance and counselling service at higher learning institutions has great potential to help learners achieve high standards in the academic, career and personal or social aspects of their lives professional guidance and counselling in universities is still relatively a new phenomenon and there is slow growth of guidance and counselling services needs to develop more facilities G&C service provided in Universities (MoEVT: 2006)

Statement of the Problem

Research conducted by Juma (2018) on the compatibility between medical students' personal values and professional ethics revealed that, there is an incompatibility between medical students' behaviour patterns and course pursuit, which finally

lead to professional misconduct, work related stress and burn out. The study recommends proper provision of guidance and counselling services to the learner including early screening and psychological assessment for proper behaviour adjustment. In this regard, the quality provision of guidance and counselling services needs reform and. This research therefore, intended to assess the quality provision of guidance and counselling services at higher learning institutions for the betterment of learner's welfare and creating psychosocial wellbeing of the employee in Tanzania and Zanzibar in particular.

The Government of Tanzania particularly in Zanzibar endorsed the provision of counselling services to its education institutions to address the psycho-social problems facing students (MOEC, 1995; MOEVT, 2009). These services are meant to assist students develop their academic, social and personal competencies. there is slow growth of guidance and counselling in educational systems attributed to lack of funds and resources, training facilities, lack of adequately qualified and solid professional counsellor within high institutions this lead to lose the quality of counselling and guidance service to provide in high institution, However ,learners today indicate a higher need for professional advice, increased need to acquire relevant career information that will enable them to pass well in their exams and seek better paid jobs (Sima,2010) in line with this situations different effort have been taken through the government and private institution by establishing different approach such as :Tanzania government has formulated guidance and counselling inside the education policy (Biswalo, 1996),some University establish their counselling and guidance centres in which universities counsellors and also lectures and they are fully occupied within teaching responsibilities and also students have a great chance to discuss and sharing ideas within the centres on how to avoid different problems such as drug abuse, bullying, un wanted pregnancies, truancy, verbal abuse, drop outs, conflict ,fighting with teachers, sexual violence ,financial problem, stress ,anxiety, depression (Zanzibar university annual report,2020)further more guidance and counselling service in Zanzibar have been introduced in educational centres since late 1990s.However,despite the availability of counselling service provided at the two private university in Zanzibar namely Zanzibar university and SUMAIT University the quality remain questionable. Therefore, this study intends to fill the gaps of what other researcher concluded through assessing the quality of guidance and counselling service, hence, this research is to offer various solutions that will help higher learning institutions strengthening the quality of counselling service within their institutions

Specific objective

To assess the nature of guidance and counselling services commonly provided in SUMAIT and Zanzibar University

Research hypothesis

What is the nature of guidance and counselling service commonly provided in SUMAIT and Zanzibar University?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

The chapter presents the literature review related to this study. The researcher presents the critical review of a diverse range of literature relevant to the research topic. The review on assessment of quality of guidance and counselling service. Relevant journals and books were cited with special relevance to the context. The theoretical framework was presented and captured the various theories that informed the study. The conceptual framework showed the relationship between independent and the dependent variable. The chapter also presented the empirical review, critique of existing literature relevant to this study and the final section was the summary of the chapter and the research gaps

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation of counseling is rooted in the various theories of guidance and counseling approach such as Egan's skilled helper solution focused counselling approach Theoretical framework refers to the theories the researcher chooses to explain the research problem (Bell, Bryman & Harley, 2018). This study used the Egan's skilled helper solution focused counselling Approach Theory to explain the quality of guidance and counseling service in university

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a model of presentation that shows the coherence through empirical research variables on how the independent variables impact upon the dependent variables of the research and illustrate the outcome. The conceptual

framework (Figure 1) was developed based on the reviewed literature where the independent variables included the implementation of quality of guidance and counselling services in university

Figure 1: Conceptual framework.

Empirical review

Ntilisinda (2017) conducted descriptive survey design on effectiveness of GCSs in facilitating learning among secondary schools students in Dodoma Municipality, Tanzania. The findings revealed that students’ lack awareness of GCSs provided in schools, students had low tendency of seeking counselling services and the types of counselling services offered to students were personal, social and academic career development. Furthermore lack of human and non-human resources were reported as a barrier to effective guidance and counselling services. Unlike the current study which concentrated on aspects of effectiveness of GCSs and students’ behavioral

Problems, the study by Ntilisinda concentrated on effectiveness of GCSs and students learning, leaving aside aspect of students’ behaviors which is important in students’ academic progress. Additionally, the study concentrated on both public and private secondary schools which are contrary to the current study which based on WSSs only

.The study was conducted at a large suburban high school in Western New York. Sculli (2011) adds that students were asked to identify their counselling needs in three categories of the career, academic, and personal/social domains. Nyutu (2007) conducted a study to develop an instrument that can be used in the identification of guidance and counselling needs of secondary school students in Kenya. The Student Counselling Needs Scale (SCNS) is a 52-item inventory which assesses the guidance and counselling needs of secondary school students in Kenya.

The initial items were pilot-tested with a group of 74 students that attended a coeducational high school in Kenya and then revised for the main study. Data were collected from 867 participants (423 males and 444 females) recruited from seven provincial schools in Kenya and analyzed using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Five factors, human relationships, career development, self-development, social values, and learning skills were assessed (Nyutu, 2007). Alpha coefficients for five SCNS subscales ranged from .83 to .88, and .94 for the whole scale. Additional analysis revealed differences by gender and school in the way students rate their needs for guidance and counselling. The findings highlighted the importance of using assessment instruments in the identification of students counselling needs. The findings also supported the recommendation that Kenya should develop guidance and counselling programmers in all schools to address students

Ouya (2006) carried out a study to investigate University students' awareness and perception of guidance and counseling services and found that many students had negative perceptions about GCS. The findings of study created greater awareness and hence developed positive perception of guidance and counseling services among college students. According to research findings, many students were not aware of guidance and counseling services at the University. Ouya (2006) also made several recommendations that would help to improve these services. They included strengthening of peer counseling services, adoption of regular and effective methods of publicity of GCS, establishing of guidance and counseling units closer to the students hostels and making guidance and counseling services gender sensitive.

Ibu & Maliki (2010) did a study to evaluate the awareness, usage and assessment of guidance services. The study was carried out among students of tertiary institutions in Plateau State of Nigeria. A total of 300 students participated in this study. They consisted of 150 male students and 150 female students, randomly selected from University of Jos, Plateau

State Polytechnic, Birinkin Ladi and Federal College of Education, Pankshing. The main finding of the study indicated that there was a significant variation in the awareness levels of the students in different tertiary institutions. It was also found out that students in the University of Jos situated in the city were more aware of the guidance services and they equally used and assessed guidance services more than students in the Polytechnics and colleges of education. It was concluded that students should be made aware of the guidance services in the university and made to use them. This information was obtained from college students whose level of understanding is expected to be high. The proposed study aims to find out from the PSP's perspective.

In the same vein, Chireshe (2006) carried out a study to examine the status of School Guidance and Counselling (SGC) services needs assessment in Zimbabwe secondary schools as perceived by school counsellors and students. The study was part of a larger study on assessing the effectiveness of school GCS in Zimbabwean secondary schools. A survey design based on two questionnaires (one for school counsellors and the other one for students) were undertaken with a sample of 950 participants (314 school counsellors and 636 students). The main findings of the study revealed that there were significant differences in the rating of the frequency of assessing the needs of students, teachers and parents among school counsellors and students (Chireshe, 2006). In addition to that, the findings showed that both school counsellors and students viewed the involvement of parents substantially negative. Lastly, they both positively viewed year end results, informal student conversation and brain storming as methods used in SGC services needs assessment. However, this study did not focus on the strategies that teachers need to adopt in order to effectively offer GCS, which the present study focused on (Okpako, 2004).

Research gap

In this study, a researcher focused on assessment of quality guidance and counselling services in universities. Various writers have examined the important role of guidance and counselling services in various perspectives. Argument is that guidance and counselling services help students overcome life challenges and associated problems that face them, both inside and outside the university environment. In the same vein, guidance and counselling services provision make students think and be respectful on the issues related to disturbances and riots while at the university. Therefore there is an urgent need of introducing and strengthening the guidance and counselling services in the Zanzibar universities to meet various needs of the students, administration and the educational system. It is unfortunate, by and large, that in most of Zanzibar's universities, policies pertinent to guidance and counselling services are still lacking.

As results professional guidance and counselling services are to date still patchy and Ineffective. Based on that, the above writers in overviews, they did not cover the knowledge gaps on assessing the quality of guidance and counselling services in universities, which this study intends to fill.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study employed a descriptive research designs the qualitative data complements the study with information on perception, opinion, attitude and experiences towards the quality of guidance and counselling services in universities. Qualitative data was collected from all targeted populations (Students, counsellor and tutor). The descriptive method was designed to expose respondents, personal feelings, image, wishes and perceptions in total ways of responding towards the research objectives. The qualitative data that have been collected into some form of explanation, understanding or interpretation of the people and situations that have been investigated (Taylor *et al.*, 2010). Data that were collected by using checklist through interviews with the head of tutor, student and counsellor were analysed through content analysis. Content analysis was used as a way of working with data from written, visual or hand material for identifying the specified traits of materials (Best & Kahn, 2006)

Sample size and sample techniques

Best and Kahn (2006) defined a sample as a small proportion of a population selected for observation and analysis, the characteristics of which can enable the researcher to make certain inferences about the population from which the sample is drawn. They maintained that there is no sample size that is best; however, a good sample should be that which reflects an actual profile of population from which it is drawn. Therefore, the sample of this study includes : (1) counsellors, (5) Lectures and (5) have been picked randomly and (14) students from two universities. All these making a sample size of 50 respondents from two universities.

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And the solving’s formula, $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$, $N =$ total population and $e =$ error tolerance.

A Researcher conducted a survey by using solving’s formula with a confidence level of 95 percent (giving a margin error of 0.05), the population size and required margin of error into the formula. The result will be the number of samples you need to take. The result of sample was as follow:

The solving’s formula is computed as $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$.

Whereas:

$n =$ no. of samples

$N =$ total population

$e =$ error margin / margin of error

Given: $N=64$ and $e=0.05$

$$n = \frac{64}{1 + 64 * 0.5^2}$$

$$n = \frac{64}{(65 * 0.5^2)}$$

$$n = 24.61 = 25 \text{ samplings}$$

Table 1. Show the total Population of the Study

Respondents	SUMAIT University	Zanzibar University
Lecturers	5	5
Student	14	14
Administrator	5	5
Counsellor	1	1
TOTAL	25	25

Source: Field Data (2022)

This study was dependent upon both secondary and primary data in order to get quality data. That means, the primary data collected through interviews and Focus Group Discussions. And secondary data was gathered through available data from various documents and academic databases done by different authors in the field of Psychology, and interpreted for the purpose of descriptive research as determined and reported on the findings.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Availability of counselling service facilities at the universities

When the students asked on availability of counselling service facilities at university, majority 69% of respondents at SUMAIT and 56% of respondents from Zanzibar University when asked, said that there is a high availability of counselling service facilities at university that operate their work to in university even though have a lot of weaknesses and cannot manage the issues such as stress the learners ability on learn and success on their results, other 31% respondent from SUMAIT University and 41% of respondent from Zanzibar University said there is no good condition of guidance and counselling facilities this is supported by the one among the student when asked on the condition of the counselling service facilities at university and said

There is available specific room of guidance and counselling unity that help students to understand themselves and enable them to deal with life experiences in a healthy manner, by being able to recognize the factors that cause problems and look for appropriate methods of resolving or avoiding the situations that may lead to unhealthy lifestyle at the university (Respondent, 43)

This revealed that the availability of counselling service facilities at universities are present and some learners were benefited from the services and have a chance to explain their personal issues while many others were not satisfied from the services.

Majority of respondent from SUMAIT and Zanzibar University said, that there is a availability of counselling service unit at university that operate their work to in university even though have a lot of weaknesses and cannot manage the issues that stress the learners ability on learn and success on their results this Support by (Choge, Tanui -okeke& Ndegwa2011) the availability of counselling service The office should be well equipped with necessary facilities like book or file shelves, table ,chairs, TV, should be well arranged to allow conduction of counselling sessions and make clients comfortable .

Types of counselling services

There are different types of counselling's services which analysed in this research such as personal/social, academic and career by which when asked to explained, one among them said:

Guidance is considered an integral part of education. Guidance helps to achieve the goals of education which include personal and social counselling, careers and education that enables a person to realize his inner potential. The main objective of education is the overall development of an individual and guidance helps to realize this objective. (Respondent, 10).

This supported by Daraba et al., (2018) said that, the counselling service motivates the learning process to the learners and influences good results to the students. Furthermore, there are many things that can influence the weakness-strength of learning motivation. In giving motivation, the factors of physical maturity, social, and psychic should be noticed. Without any physical preparation for learning, students' motivation in learning will be decreased. That issue will give an impact to social relations in the learning, that are less optimal, and the learning result will not be maximum. Psychological condition also becomes an important factor. A good mental health will ease students facing every challenge in the learning activity (Parkinson, 1995). This revealed that Guidance as a process helps an individual to make the right decisions in various aspects of life so that a balanced development of the individual can be facilitated Furthermore, Guidance is considered an integral part of education and helps to achieve the goals of education which include enabling a person to realize his inner potential.

Status of Attendance guidance and counselling service

Majority of respondents from SUMAIT and Zanzibar University did not attend counselling services and this supported by (Borrow1983) states that most students in university do not attend university counselling services properly; hence, it affects their behaviour and discipline in university. Similarly, Sophie et al., (2013) at their study in Zambia, found out that 72% of students in private universities indicated that their institutions have a counselling service, whereas 53% of public students indicated that their university has counselling services. This indicate that the counselling provided at the Zanzibar and SUMAIT universities do not meet the level required by the pupils due to time

Counselling service motivating the learning process

The respondents asked to bring their views on the counselling service motivating the learning process majority 59% of the respondent from SUMAIT University and 45% from Zanzibar university said there is a highly influence of counselling service motivating the learning process, other 30% of the respondent from SUMAIT University 35% from Zanzibar University said there is no influence and the rest 11% of respondents from SUMAIT university and 20%from Zanzibar University asked were not have an idea on it.

The guidance program which does not give information service will deter students from growing further, because they need a chance to learn data and facts which can influence their way of life. (Respondent, 5)

This supported by Philip (1992) learning motivation is one of the most important factors for achieving learning success. It is related to aspects of physical preparation, attention, interest, skills, and self-control of the environment in learning, counselling services information provides cognitive understanding that can shape active and productive learning attitudes and behaviours in the dynamics of study groups. Moreover, proficiency and learning skills that are well formed will ease students in learning. Hence, that ease brings students enjoyment in learning, if the students are happy in learning, then they are motivated to actively participate in the learning activity. Students who are motivated to participate actively in the learning process will influence students' self-recognition that at the end they get involved and needed in the learning process so that the spirit and passion in the learning will be created. Students learnt the aspects of learning motivation. Also, will improve the physical preparation, attention, interest, skill, and self-controlling towards learning circumstances .

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

The conclusions of this study are more based from the findings of this study;

Types of counselling services provided in these universities are based on the condition of counselling facilities at the university in which it is practices have been in existence for a long time and passed on from one intake of new students to another but have a lot of weaknesses and cannot influence the student's ability on learn, to resolve their own problems and success form their academic results.

Status of attendance in guidance and counselling service in the Zanzibar University and SUMAIT Universities is not good. This is because the majority of students in university do not attend university counselling services properly and then took much time in watching social media

Recommendations

From the above conclusion, the following recommendations are made to assist the development planners, policy makers and development agencies for improvement of universities undertaken by Zanzibar University and SUMAIT University and the rest part of the universities;

The management of Zanzibar University and SUMAIT Universities should improve the environments in guidance and counselling service so as the majority of students in university be influenced to attend university guidance and counselling service properly and reduce much time spent watching social media. Status of attendance in guidance and counselling service.

Recommendations for Further Research

The findings presented in this study are a result of micro and cross-sectional survey design where data were collected at one point in time from two universities. The major problem of micro and cross-sectional studies is that they cannot be representative of the total population of universities in Zanzibar- The findings presented in this study are a result of micro and cross-sectional survey design where data were collected at one point in time from two universities. The major problem of micro and cross-sectional studies is that they cannot be representative of the total population of universities in Zanzibar-Tanzania. In this case there is a direct need for more longitudinal studies on the subject in other parts of the country to enable generalization of observations.

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